

Pixels – So basic but so confusing

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In the very first part of this series, we concisely explored the nature of electromagnetic radiation and explained why and how the reflection of its optical part governs the creation of most remote sensing products. A perfect and prevalent example of the latter is the acquisition of a digital photograph. Any photograph, whether airborne, spaceborne or terrestrial, records how an object or a scene interacts with all kinds of radiant energy (amongst many other interactions such as those taking place in the atmosphere and inside the camera). Even though that might seem obvious, the constant increase of digital cameras in all forms and shapes makes us too often unaware of the complex events that take place under the hood of a camera. All these events make up the **imaging chain** or **imaging pipeline**.

To cover all aspects of the whole imaging pipeline comprehensively is impossible in just a few pages. Let us, therefore, mainly focus on the output of such an imaging pipeline: a digital photograph (or more generally a digital image). Starting from the fundamentals of an imaging sensor, this article will provide some insights into the basic building blocks of any image: **pixels**. The concepts that are introduced here and in the first entry will prove essential for most of the future entries in this series.

1 Digital imaging sensors

1.1 Photosites

Analogue signals are continuous and exist in nature as functions of space and time. Digital signals are found inside computers and merely a collection of discrete states. Once an analogue signal is **digitised**, perfect clones become possible. The digital product is, however, always an approximation of the analogue reality because this numerical translation is accomplished by the processes **sampling** and **quantisation** (both explained below). The analogue signal that is digitally captured by photography or any other form of optical imaging is the continuously varying electromagnetic radiation (denoted **spectral radiance $L(\lambda)$** in the previous article) that is reflected or emitted by the scene/object under study. A digital ultraviolet, visible or infrared image is generated by converting that particular type of radiant energy into an electrical output signal which is then digitised.

All cameras comprise optical elements such as lenses and filters that gather electromagnetic radiation and focus it onto its imaging sensor. For many applications such as conventional photography, these imaging sensors consist of a two-dimensional array of individual photon sensing sites or **photosites** (Figure 1). The key component of such a photosite is the photodetector, which collects the electromagnetic radiation during the exposure time. Depending on the sensor design, the individual photosites may contain more or less circuitry, and the photon-receiving surface area of the photodetector may be smaller or larger. Throughout the years, academia and industry proposed diverse photosite arrangements and photodetector designs to achieve specific performances (e.g. increase the image's spatial resolution or optimise the spectral sensitivity of the imaging sensor).

Most photo cameras feature an imaging sensor in which one photodetector contributes one effective pixel in the final image. For instance, a 24-megapixel digital camera has an imaging sensor built-up by at least 24 million photosites/photodetectors that are equally distributed in rows and columns (for instance: 6000 columns x 4000 rows). "At least" is essential here, since additional photosites take care of tasks like white balancing and dark signal correction. The distance from the centre of one photosite to the centre of an adjacent element is denoted the **photosite/detector pitch** or the **inter-detector spacing** (Figure 1), a metric which will be vital when talking about spatial resolving power.

1.2 Spectral bands

Every imaging sensor will detect the incoming electromagnetic radiance in specific spectral regions. Conventional photo and video cameras acquire visible electromagnetic radiation (i.e. light) in three 100-nm-wide spectral bands, being the blue waveband (with wavelengths from 400 nm to 500 nm), the green (500 nm-600 nm) and red (600 nm-700 nm) spectrum (Figure 1). Since every pixel of a conventional photograph holds one digital number for the Red, one for the Green and one for the Blue spectral band, they are often called RGB images. The reasons as to why precisely these bands are captured go beyond this entry.

Figure 1 The relative spectral response curves and image sensor layout of a typical off-the-shelf digital photo camera.

To achieve RGB images, off-the-shelf digital photo and video cameras feature an imaging sensor with a filter on top that blocks non-visible electromagnetic radiation (the so-called hot mirror; Figure 1). Without this filter, the sensor would also detect near-ultraviolet and near-infrared radiation, which would make it impossible to render the scene colours as humans perceive them. As depicted in Figure 1, none of the photosites captures all three visible bands. A mosaic of thin coloured filters ensures that only one particular part of the incident radiant energy is captured per photosite. Digital cameras mainly use a so-called **Bayer pattern** which features twice as many green filters as blue or red ones. Since every pixel of an RGB image must feature three values per pixel, the two missing components are interpolated from the neighbouring photosites.

Most remote sensing instruments can image invisible radiation because particular object properties might only (or better) be discernible in these parts of the electromagnetic spectrum (e.g. detecting water in the near-infrared band). Moreover, many sensors also capture incoming radiant energy in more than three spectral bands. The amount of spectral bands is one of the distinguishing factors that denote an imaging system as “multi” or “hyper”. A multi-spectral device acquires electromagnetic radiation in four to circa ten adjacent spectral bands that are about 100 nm wide and often feature a small spectral gap in between them (e.g. [730 nm–850 nm] or [1050 nm–1200 nm]). Hyper-spectral imaging extends this multi-spectral concept by capturing spectral data in at least ten (nearly) contiguous (i.e. adjacent and not overlapping) narrow spectral channels.

2 Pixels: quantised samples that need reconstruction

Whatever the type of imaging sensor, they all create a digital image. The fundamental building blocks of any digital image are called **pixels** or **pels**, coined terms for picture elements. In contrast to popular belief, pixels do not occupy any area. They are neither rectangular, square or round (for more info, see the seminal paper of Smith referenced below). Pixels are merely **dimensionless, quantised samples** that digitally represent an analogous electromagnetic signal. After the acquisition of those pixels, people want to view them on a screen. This means that those pixels – which digitally represent the original analogue signal – are used to **reconstruct** that initial analogue signal. The next sections focus on these three stages of digital imaging: sampling, quantisation and reconstruction.

2.1 Sampling

Sampling is an elementary process that must be performed when measuring a property of the physical world since no digital instrument can measure a signal with infinite resolving power. However, the nature of this sampling should largely be determined by the spatial or spatio-temporal characteristics of the sampled property. To create a digital image, a digital imager measures the continuous but varying electromagnetic radiation – which emanates from individual adjacent scene points – by collecting incoming photons over the finite area of every photosite and in some pre-defined spectral wavebands. This process lasts as long as the exposure lasts (e.g. 1/250 s). All the absorbed photons generate a charge in every photodetector that is linearly proportional to the amount of incoming radiation. After the exposure, the charge of every single detector is read out and represents a sample of the electromagnetic energy originating from the imaged scene (see Figure 2).

In other words, photographic pixels are created by sampling the scene in the space, spectral and time dimensions. A digital photograph is thus never a very accurate reproduction (in absolute terms), since its pixels represent averages in time, in spectral range and in space.

Figure 2 Digitising an analogue, spatially varying signal into a collection of 3-bit point samples or pixels.

A pixel is often thought of as a square for several reasons. One of them is rooted in this sampling process. To obtain sufficient radiation, the samples created by imaging sensors are averaged photon counts over the finite area of the photosite. Since the latter is usually square (but it can also be rectangular or even octagonal shaped), a pixel is thought of as square, whereas in fact, the more or less square area is the contribution to the pixel's value. A pixel thus remains a point sample, but the

contribution to it is the photon arrival integrated over a particular area. (Note that although the latter is square, the photon contribution is somewhat Gaussian; the reason for this falls, again, outside the scope of this article).

Figure 3 The complete imaging chain: a digital camera digitises an analogous real-world scene which gets reconstructed on a monitor. The lower part of the illustration depicts the overall pipeline (from left to right), including the pixel creation stage. On top, the imaging chain is broken down into its radiometric components. For convenience, also the corresponding photometric quantities and units are given since these apply when imaging visible radiation.

2.2 Quantisation

In the context of imaging, sampling refers to the process of transforming the continuous analogue signal into a discrete signal. Afterwards, these sample values (remember, the charges) have to be mapped onto a discrete set of values by a process called **quantisation**. The final image pixels are thus created by quantising every sample to a discrete **digital/data number (DN)** by the **analogue-to-digital converter (ADC)**. The total range of different tones or quantisation values an ADC can create is termed the **tonal range**. The ADC's bit depth entirely determines the tonal range of the image: quantisation with N bits rounds all possible charges to these 2^N values. For example, the 3-bit ADC in Figure 2 can discriminate 2^3 tones, and every pixel will get one of those eight possible discrete DNs.

Pixels are thus sampled and quantised versions of a continuous analogue signal. These samples are determined by a pair of pixel coordinates (r , c indicating row and column) and a specific value (the DN) or grouping of values that contains data about the measured physical quantity. An array of these pixels is called a digital image, mathematically represented as an $M \times N$ matrix of numbers, M and N indicating the image dimensions in pixels. Consider Figure 2 for a 1×15 series of pixels, while the matrix in Figure 3 shows an image of 8×16 pixels.

Just as a pixel of a standard colour photograph contains three DNs at the same location to represent the radiation captured in three spectral bands, a greyscale image consists of one DN per pixel. Digital images can thus be represented by O matrices of $M \times N$ elements, in which O equals the number of spectral bands (for display purposes, Figure 3 shows the matrix with pixels of one band only).

3 Reconstruction for image display

Any digital photograph is a sampled (spatially, spectrally and temporally) and quantised (defined by the number of bits) representations of a continuous real-world scene, defined by a multidimensional matrix of numbers. Using these samples, the original scene can be reconstructed on the display device (such as a computer monitor, camera display or television). It is in this displaying step that originates the main reason for the square pixel misconception, since magnifying an image on any display often gives birth to the appearance of tiny squares. The more zoom is applied, the more prominent these squares seem to become and the more the pixel is apparently magnified. The appearing squares can, however, be explained by the algorithm used during this reconstruction step.

Only when every pixel lines up with one triad of the display (one triad is needed to show one pixel), all image data are shown. In most cases, the image's pixel count (i.e. all image pixels) is much larger than the monitor's triad count. For example, 24 megapixels are very common these days, whereas most monitors can only display about 2-megapixels (a full HD monitor with 1920 by 1080 triads) or slightly over 8-megapixels (a 4K monitor featuring 3840 by 2160 triads). In both cases, many image pixels are left out when displaying the complete image. When zooming in, a point is achieved at which there are more triads in the display than there are pixels in the portion of the image that is looked at. To remedy this and still display a continuous representation of the scene, new pixel values are computed to fill in the gaps between the other pixels. This operation, known as **interpolation**, is performed every time the monitor triads do not line up exactly with the image pixels.

A **reconstruction filter** executes the reconstruction (or recovery) of the continuous scene representation by interpolating between the discrete samples. Various reconstruction filters exist, all with their pros and cons, but the most common is the **box filter** (Figure 4). This reconstruction filter – whose kernel is also displayed in Figure 4 – applies a **nearest neighbour interpolation** by merely duplicating the original pixel value (i.e. at sample number 0) between the location of the original pixel and its nearest neighbouring locations that need a value to be assigned to them (i.e. from -0.5 to 0.5). Since the same procedure happens with all image pixels, sample number 1 will replicate its value in the zone [0.5, 1.5]. The area between the original pixels 0 and 1 is, therefore, nicely divided in two. After applying this operation in both width and height and looking at the filter kernel from above, one would see that the footprint of this box filter is square. Since its application simply repeats the pixel value of the nearest pixel, zooming in creates an individual square raster cell around each sample location. As such, it became a well-established misconception that this cell equals the dimension of that pixel (as pixels are dimensionless).

In the last few decades, this idea was reinforced by the increasing use of spatial data. In the case of a box reconstruction filter, the reconstruction generates an output that resembles the raster files typically known from a Geographical Information System (GIS). Regular GIS raster layers also consist of raster cells with one specific value per cell. In the case of nearest neighbour interpolation, the reconstructed image also seems to feature those cells that have one value identical to the pixel's DN. However, this cell is just a pixel reconstruction artefact and has nothing to do with the size of the pixel itself. Since a nearest neighbour reconstruction is fast, it is by default implemented in any image viewing software. However, it offers the lowest quality reconstruction of the original signal.

Much better are **bilinear** and **bicubic interpolations**, executed by the tent-filter and a bicubic spline. Both filters do not have a square footprint and will thus interpolate an average pixel value based on the pixel's neighbours. The result is a less blocky reconstruction with much smoother transitions between the samples. In other words: all little squares are gone and together with it the erroneous concept of pixel size (Figure 4). Bicubic interpolation is the more accurate reconstruction filter but comes at the cost of higher computational complexity, thereby leading to slower response times.

Figure 4 Different interpolators used in image reconstruction. The pixels on which these reconstructions are based are indicated in the left image.

More advanced image viewing and GIS software often offer bilinear and bicubic reconstruction filters to get rid of the square appearance when zooming in. A good example is the trendy image-based modelling package Agisoft PhotoScan, which enables the user to set the interpolation mode when looking at individual photographs. Put it first on nearest neighbour and afterwards on bicubic. With the last setting active, try to find square pixels!

4 Reference

Smith, A.R., 1995. A Pixel Is Not A Little Square, A Pixel Is Not A Little Square, A Pixel Is Not A Little Square! (And a Voxel is Not a Little Cube). Microsoft Technical Memo 6. Microsoft, 11 pp.